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- Poetry
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Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. ALEXANDER N. MORADOS

Associate Professor V

Camiguin Polytechnic State College

alexandermorados8@gmail.com

“THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURISTS IN SHAPING THE FUTURE OF PHILIPPINE AGRICULTURE”

Republic Act No. 12215 also known as the Philippine Agriculturist Act of 2025, was signed into law on May 29, 2025 by President Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr. The landmark law was principally sponsored by Senator Juan Miguel Zubiri, an agriculturist who cited it as “a long overdue” recognition of the vital role of agriculturist in national development”. The said act regulates the practice of agriculture profession in the country, creating a Professional Regulatory Board of Agriculture to oversee the licensure, registration and practice of registered agriculturist.

As the Philippine agricultural sector faces various challenges such as climate change, land degradation and an aging population of farmers, agriculturist play a vital role in shaping the future of the country’s “backbone of economy”. Agriculturists are considered as key to driving innovation and sustainability. They are professionals who are into teaching in the basic and higher education levels, conduct research and development in the laboratory and in the field, engage in extension and advisory services and involve in the production of food, feed, fuel and fiber.

Agriculturists are agents of modernizing agricultural practices by introducing new and relevant farming technologies to increase crop and animal production, food processing, distribution and marketing and to decrease the use of water, chemical fertilizers and pesticides. The adoption of climate-resilient crop cultivar and animal breeds can help farmers mitigate the effects of climate change and other weather disturbances. With the use of ICT and AI, they can revolutionize agriculture through precision farming, crop, soil and animal health monitoring and automating machines. Through their time, efforts and skills and in cooperation with relevant stakeholders, food security can be achieved in every home and community.

Agriculturists as agents of rural development can contribute to job creation by training farmers, homemakers, and out of school youth thus, sustaining livelihoods and income generation and thereby enhancing the quality of life of the people. As policy advocates for ecological agriculture in every small family farms, agriculturists can raise the level of community awareness, attitude and practices toward inclusive and sustainable food production system. The voices of the agriculturists the private sectors, non-government organizations, local government units, national government agencies and the academe can make change towards policy formulation, enhancement and implementation for a vibrant Philippine Agriculture today and in the future.

